

Unsteady Electromagnetic Flow of Williamson Nanofluid through Porous Media Over A Vertical Stretching Sheet with Heat and Mass Transfer

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Abstract

This research based on study of influences of inclined magnetic field , electric field on flow of incompressible, unsteady Williamson nano fluid over a vertically stretching surface embedded in a porous medium. Firstly, the highly non-linear partial differential equations transformed into set of dimensionless ordinary differential equations and numerically solve with MATLAB function. The variation in velocity, temperature and concentration with numerous physical parameters are presented through graphs and tables. The numerical distribution of reduced skin-friction coefficient, Nusselt number and local Sherwood number for various physical parameter are described through tables.

Keywords

Electromagnetic, Williamson, Vertical Stretching, Mass Transfer.

Introduction

Due to broad area of technical and industrial applications nanofluids have great importance hence it is become more interesting topic of research for mathematical and physical researchers. It is also known as a type of heat transfer fluid with higher thermal conductivity. In 1959 nanotechnology is firstly introduced by Richard Feynman here we have consider Williamson fluid model for research , it is a non-Newtonian fluid with shear thinning. In 1929 Williamson model is formed by Williamson [1] for study of behavior of pseudoplastic fluids with flow characteristics. Williamson nano fluid is settled in 2D with magnetic flow stream which passes through a stretching surface embedded in porous medium. Choi et al[2] worked for enhancing thermal conductivity of fluids and found results as nano fluids.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the unsteady electromagnetic flow of Williamson nanofluid through porous media over a vertical stretching sheet with heat and mass transfer.

Review of Literature

Nadeem et al[3] analyze heat transfer with flow of Williamson nanofluids and Muthuraj et al [4] studied unsteady flow of Williamson fluid with nanoparticle through a vertical plate in porous media. Hayat et al[5] explored the effects of electric and magnetic field in unsteady flow of Williamson fluid with thermal radiation. Kebede et al [6] demonstrated unsteady flow of Williamson nanofluid with thermal radiation , magnetic field and chemical reaction with porosity. Hamid et al [7] evaluated time dependent flow of Williamson nanofluid with consideration of thermal radiation and ohmic dissipation. Hashim et al[8] studied the effect of variable thermal conductivity and magnetic field on time dependent flow of Williamson nanofluid. Hamid et al[9] examined heat source/sink and thermal radiation effects on unsteady Williamson flow of nanofluid between two infinite plates. Raghunath[10] explored impacts of heat source/sink, Soret and chemical reaction on MHD flow of nanofluid through a vertical plate embedded in porous media. Azmi et al. [11] studied stagnation point flow of Maxwell nanofluid through aligned plate. Further, Hunegnaw [12] inspected about unsteady flow of Williamson nanofluid with viscous dissipation through a stretchable sheet in porous media and Maiti et al.[13] investigated time dependent MHD flow of Williamson fluid in presence of nanoparticle with heat transfer.

The study of magnetic field and electric field effects on flow of non-Newtonian fluid through a vertically stretchable sheet in porous media have great importance in field of business and industry hence in recent years many researchers taking interest in this research topic. For exemplification , Shafiq et al. [14]demonstrated the magnetic field effect on Williamson fluid flow past a radiative surface and Shrinu et al. [15] made an analysis of velocity, thermal and concentration with effect of radiation and inclined magnetic field on flow of Williamson fluid .Reddy et al.[16] investigated an unsteady flow of incompressible Newtonian fluid with magnetic field and heat flux and Shah et al.[17] derived. Shateyi

et al. [18] numerically analyze MHD Williamson fluid flow through a stretchable surface embedded in porous media.

Due to various applications in industry and business field there are many research studies are performed on unsteady flow of Williamson nano fluid over a vertical

stretching sheet. Originality of this article is the inclusion of Brownian and thermophoresis effects with also taking the effects of inclined magnetic field, thermal radiation, chemical reaction and heat source/sink parameters are analyzed in this model. The system of highly coupled non-linear partial differential equations which describe current study converted into set of non-linear ordinary differential equations by using acceptable similarity transformations and then solved by bvp4c solver embedded in MATLAB. The numerical and analytical results as effects of various physical parameters on velocity, temperature and concentration profiles are displayed through graphs and tables.

Analysis

We have consider two dimensional unsteady electrically conducting flow of Williamson nanofluid through a porous stretching sheet with thermal slip condition. The cartesian coordinates are taken in a way as x-axis is along stretching sheet and y-axis along normal to vertical stretching sheet. In current study the effect of viscous dissipation , heat source/sink and thermal radiation. Here the fluid is electrically conducting and a uniform transverse magnetic field B and electric field E considered. The systematic diagram of this flow field is given in figure (a).

Figure (a): Flow model of problem

We get the following set of governing equations with above mentioned assumptions

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + 2\theta \Gamma \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\sigma}{\rho} \sin^2 \omega (E_0 B_0 - B_0^2 u) - \frac{\theta u}{K_1} + g\beta_T (T - T_\infty) + g\beta_C (C - C_\infty), \tag{2}$$

$$\rho C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \mu_0 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \mu_0 \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^3 + \sin^2 \omega (u B_0 - E_0)^2 - \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} + Q_0 (T - T_\infty) + \tau \left[D_m \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right], \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D_m \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} - K' (C - C_\infty) + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2}, \tag{4}$$

Here u and v are velocity components in x and y directions , respectively and θ is the kinematic viscosity , Γ is Maxwell parameter, D_m is the Brownian diffusion coefficient and D_T is thermophoresis diffusion coefficient.

Boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= L_1 \left(\mu_0 \left\{ \frac{\partial u(x,0)}{\partial y} + \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial u(x,0)}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right\} \right) + U_w, \\ v(x, 0) &= V_w = -\frac{v_0}{(1-c_1 t)^{1/2}}, \quad -k_f \frac{\partial T(x,0)}{\partial y} = h_f (T_w - T) + L_2 \frac{\partial T(x,0)}{\partial y}, \quad -D_m \frac{\partial C(x,0)}{\partial y} = k_m (C_w - C) + L_3 \frac{\partial C(x,0)}{\partial y}, \\ u(x, y \rightarrow \infty) &\rightarrow 0, \quad T(x, y \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow T_\infty, \quad C(x, y \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow C_\infty, \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Here V_w represents suction ($V_w > 0$) or injection ($V_w < 0$) of mass on surface and U_w is variable stretching velocity and T_w is variable wall temperature are given as

$$U_w(x, t) = \frac{a_1 x}{1-c_1 t}, \quad T_w(x, t) = T_\infty + T_0 \frac{a_1 x}{2\theta(1-c_1 t)^2}, \quad C_w(x, t) = C_\infty + C_0 \frac{a_1 x}{2\theta(1-c_1 t)^2},$$

The suitable similarity transformation are as follows

$$\zeta = \sqrt{\frac{U_w}{x\theta}} y, \quad \psi = \sqrt{\theta x U_w} f(\zeta), \quad \theta(\zeta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, \quad \Phi(\zeta) = \frac{C - C_\infty}{C_w - C_\infty}, \tag{6}$$

With

$$u = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}, \quad v = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x'}$$

With the help of above similarity transformation the equations 1-5 reduces as

$$(1+2We f'')f'''' + ff'' - (f')^2 - s(f' + \frac{\zeta}{2}f'') + M^2 \sin^2 \varpi (E - f') + \lambda_1 \theta + \lambda_2 \Phi - Kf' = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr}(1+\frac{4R}{3})\theta'' + f\theta' - \frac{S}{2}\zeta\theta' - (2s + f')\theta' + Ec(f'')^2 + We(f'')^3 + M^2 Ec \sin^2 \varpi (f' - E)^2 + Q\theta + Nb\theta'\Phi' + Nt(\theta')^2 = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\Phi'' + \frac{Nt}{Nb}\theta'' + Sc[f\Phi' - 2f'\Phi - \frac{S_1}{2}(3\Phi + \zeta\Phi') - Kr\Phi] = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$f(0) = A, \quad f'(0) = 1 + \gamma[f''(0) + We\{f''(0)\}^2]$$

$$\theta'(0) = \frac{-Bi_1[1-\theta(0)]}{1+\alpha},$$

$$\Phi'(0) = \frac{-Bi_2[1-\Phi(0)]}{1+\beta},$$

$$f' \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta \rightarrow 0, \quad \Phi \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{When} \quad \zeta \rightarrow \infty, \quad (10)$$

Where

$$We(\text{Weissenberg number}) = \Gamma U_w \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_1}{\vartheta(1-c_1 t)'}}$$

$$M^2(\text{Magnetic parameter}) = \frac{\sigma B_0^2(1-c_1 t)}{\rho \alpha_1},$$

$$E(\text{Local electric number}) = \frac{E_0(1-c_1 t)}{B_0 \alpha_1 x},$$

$$A(\text{suction / injection parameter}) = \frac{v_0}{a\vartheta'}$$

$$s(\text{Unsteadiness parameter}) = \frac{c_1}{a_1},$$

$$\gamma(\text{Velocity slip number}) = \mu_0 L_1 \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_1}{\vartheta(1-c_1 t)'}}$$

$$\lambda_1(\text{Thermal buoyancy parameter}) = \frac{g\beta_T T_0}{2\alpha_1 \vartheta'}$$

$$\lambda_2(\text{Solutal buoyancy parameter}) = \frac{g\beta_C C_0}{2\alpha_1 \vartheta'}$$

$$K(\text{Permeability parameter}) = \frac{\vartheta}{K_1 \alpha_1},$$

$$R(\text{Radiation parameter}) = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{k^* k},$$

$$Pr(\text{Prandtl number}) = \frac{\mu_0 c_p}{k},$$

$$Nb(\text{Brownian motion parameter}) = \frac{\tau D_m (C_w - C_\infty)}{\vartheta}$$

$$Nt(\text{Thermophoresis parameter}) = \frac{\tau D_T (T_w - T_\infty)}{\vartheta T_\infty},$$

$$\alpha(\text{Thermal slip number}) = \frac{L_2}{k_f'}$$

$$\beta(\text{Thermal slip number}) = \frac{L_3}{D_m},$$

$$Bi_1(\text{Biot number}) = \frac{h_f}{k_f} \sqrt{\frac{\vartheta x}{U_w'}}$$

$$Bi_2(\text{Biot number}) = \frac{k_m}{D_m} \sqrt{\frac{\vartheta x}{U_w'}}$$

$$Q(\text{Heat source/sink parameter}) = Q_0 \frac{(1-c_1 t)}{\rho^* c_p \alpha_1},$$

$$Ec(\text{Eckert number}) = \frac{U_w^2}{c_p (T_w - T_\infty)'}$$

$$Sc(\text{Schmidt number}) = \frac{\vartheta}{D_m},$$

$$Kr(\text{Chemical reaction parameter}) = K' \frac{(1-c_1 t)}{\alpha_1},$$

The skin friction , local Nusselt number and local Sherwood number are describe as

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho^* U_w^2}, \quad Nu_x = \frac{xq_w}{k(T_w - T_\infty)}, \quad Sh_x = \frac{xq_m}{D_m(C_w - C_\infty)} \quad (11)$$

By using equation (6), we have

$$Re_x^{1/2} C_f = [f''(0) + We\{f''(0)\}^2],$$

$$Nu_x = -Re_x^{1/2} \left(1 + \frac{4R}{3}\right) \theta'(0), \quad Sh_x = -Re_x^{1/2} \Phi'(0)$$

$$\text{Where } Re_x(\text{Local Reynold number}) = \frac{U_w x}{\vartheta}$$

Result and Discussion

In this study we have investigated the influence of numerous physical parameters on fluid flow and the results as impact of parameters on velocity, temperature and concentration of time dependent flow of Maxwell nanofluid as well as skin friction , local Nusselt and Sherwood numbers presented via graphs and tables. the table shows the effects of physical parameters on skin friction, local Nusselt number and Sherwood number. The values of various physical parameters employed in current study taken as $M = 0.2, \beta = 0.2, A = 0.4, We = 0.2, \gamma = 0.2, \lambda_1 = 0.1, \lambda_2 = 0.1, Bi_1 = 0.2, Bi_2 =$

$$0.2, Pr = 2, Nt = 0.5, Q = 0.5, Sc = 0.2, K = 0.2, Nb = 2, E = 0.5, Kr = 0.2, \omega = \frac{\pi}{6}, s = 0.3, Ec = 0.5, R = 0.3, \alpha = 0.2.$$

Figure 1: Velocity across s

Figure 2: Velocity across M

Figure 3: Velocity across A

Figure(1) scrutinize the impact of Unsteadiness parameter for both cases as $\omega = \pi/2$ and $\omega = \pi/4$ on velocity of fluid and we have observed that velocity decreases by growing values of Unsteadiness parameter for both cases. Figure(2) depicted that velocity profiles lessening with rising values of magnetic parameter for both conditions this fact describe as transverse magnetic field enhances Lorentz force which is a resistive force suppress the velocity of fluid. It is noted in figure(3) that growing values of suction/injection parameter reducing the velocity of fluid for both situations i.e. non inclined MHD and inclined MHD. It is also notable from figure(4) that fluid velocity reduced with increasing values of Weissenberg parameter for both situations i.e. $\omega = \pi/2$ and $\omega = \pi/6$. It is clear by definition of

We that it is ratio of relaxation time to specific time so rising values of We indicate lowering values of specific process time which leads to reduce velocity. The impact of velocity slip number is plotted in figure (5) and observed a reduction in fluid velocity with rising values of velocity slip number for aligned MHD ($\omega = \pi/6$) and non aligned MHD ($\omega = \pi/2$)

In figure(6) –(7) graphs shows the effects of thermal buoyancy and solutal buoyancy parameter on velocity of fluid and noticed that fluid velocity elevated

with rising values of both parameters for inclined and non-inclined MHD. Variation in fluid temperature with Biot number expressed by figure(8) and observed an elevation in temperature with a rise in Biot number. Effect of Biot number and slip number on concentration presented via figure(9)-(10) and shows that concentration increases and decreases with greater values of Biot number and slip number, respectively. Figure(11) demonstrates how the Prandtl number affected the fluid temperature and graph shows that higher values of Prandtl number reduces temperature hence heat transfer rate of

the fluid increases.

Figure (12)-(13) illustrates variation in temperature and concentration of nanofluid with enhancing values of Thermophoresis parameter , respectively and we have observed that as Thermophoresis parameter enlarges, both temperature and concentration of nanofluid increases for both situations of inclination parameter ω . Effect of permeability parameter on fluid velocity plotted in figure(14) and reveals that velocity reduces in the boundary layer with growing values of K . It is due to amplification of porous layer with an elevation of K.

Figure 4: Velocity across We

Figure 5: Velocity across γ

Figure 6: Velocity across λ_1

Figure 7: Velocity across λ_2

Figure 8: Temperature across Bi_1

Figure 9: Concentration across Bi_2

Figure 10: Concentration across β

Figure 11: Temperature across Pr

Figure 12: Temperature across Nt

Figure 13: Concentration across Nt

Figure 14: Velocity across K

Figure 15: Temperature across Nb

Figure 16: Concentration across Nb

Figure 17: Velocity across E

Figure 18: Temperature across R

Figure (15)-(16) reveals how the Brownian motion parameter affected the temperature and concentration when $\omega = \pi/2$ and $\omega = \pi/6$ of nanoparticle and we have noticed that an enhancement in Nb increases fluid temperature and decreases concentration of nanoparticle, it is because of an increment in random motion of nanoparticles so collision of particles improves. In figure (17), it is notable that the rising values of local electric number enhances fluid velocity for both situations of inclination parameter. Behavior of

fluid temperature with thermal radiation parameter and heat source/sink parameter is plotted in figure(18)-(19) and noticed an elevation in fluid temperature with growing values of both parameters , this is due to heat generation into the fluid by an increase in R. Now, figure (20)-(21) shows reduction in concentration with growing values of chemical reaction parameter and Schmidt number and figure (22)-(24)represents influences of aligned angle(ω) on fluid velocity, temperature and concentration and it is notable that fluid velocity and temperature are increases and concentration of nanoparticle decreases with higher values of ω . Figure (25) demonstrates that an enhancement in thermal slip number reduces fluid temperature.

Figure19:Temperature across Q

Figure20: Concentration across Kr

Figure21:Concentration across Sc

Figure22:Velocity across ω

Figure23:Temperature across ω

Figure24:Concentration across ω

Figure25:Temperature across α

Table 1: Numerical values of $Re_x^{1/2} C_f$ for different values of physical parameters

We	A	s	M	E	γ	$-Re_x^{1/2} C_f$	$-Re_x^{1/2} C_f$
						$\omega = \pi/2$	$\omega = \pi/6$
0.1						0.7631	0.7552
0.2						0.8187	0.8092
0.3						0.9057	0.8930
0.4						1.1233	1.1233
	-0.3					0.8525	0.8429
	-0.1					0.9262	0.9164
	0.0					0.9664	0.9565
	0.1					1.0089	0.9989
	0.3					1.1017	1.0914
		0.2				0.7768	0.7673
		0.4				0.8554	0.8462
		0.6				0.9227	0.9139
			0.1			0.8092	0.8068
			0.2			0.8187	0.8092
			0.3			0.8342	0.8131
				0.2		0.8130	0.8078
				0.4		0.8069	0.8062
				0.6		0.8006	0.8046
					0.0	1.2091	1.1915
					0.1	1.0398	1.0261
					0.2	0.9150	0.9038
					0.3	0.8187	0.8092

Table 2: Numerical values of Nu_x and Sh_x for different values of physical parameters

Pr	Nb	Nt	Bi_1	Bi_2	α	β	Sc	$-Nu_x$	$-Nu_x$	$-Sh_x$	$-Sh_x$
								$\omega = \frac{\pi}{2}$	$\omega = \frac{\pi}{6}$	$\omega = \frac{\pi}{2}$	$\omega = \frac{\pi}{6}$
0.8								0.1115	0.1109	0.1232	0.1257
0.9								0.1125	0.1119	0.1232	0.1257
1.0								0.1133	0.1126	0.1231	0.1256
	0.2							0.1155	0.1165	0.1032	0.1024
	0.4							0.1146	0.1156	0.1157	0.1153
	0.6							0.1141	0.1150	0.1198	0.1196
		0.2						0.1121	0.1131	0.1270	0.1270
		0.4						0.1118	0.1128	0.1261	0.1261
		0.6						0.1115	0.1125	0.1252	0.1252
			0.2					0.1117	0.1126	0.1256	0.1256
			0.4					0.1813	0.1831	0.1236	0.1235
			0.6					0.2287	0.2310	0.1222	0.1221
				0.2				0.1117	0.1126	0.1256	0.1256
				0.4				0.1102	0.1112	0.2044	0.2045
				0.6				0.1092	0.1102	0.2585	0.2587
					0.1			0.1193	0.1204	0.1254	0.1254
					0.2			0.1117	0.1126	0.1256	0.1256
					0.3			0.1049	0.1058	0.1259	0.1259
						0.1		0.1115	0.1125	0.1343	0.1343
						0.2		0.1117	0.1126	0.1256	0.1250
						0.3		0.1118	0.1128	0.1181	0.1181
							1	0.1116	0.1126	0.1472	0.1472
							2	0.1118	0.1128	0.1523	0.1523
							3	0.1120	0.1130	0.1545	0.1545

Table 1 indicates the effects of We , A , s , M , E and γ on skin friction coefficient for non-inclined and inclined magnetic field, respectively. We have observed that reduced skin friction enlarges with growing values of We , A , s , M and reduces with E and γ for both cases.

Table 2 describes variation in local Nusselt number and Sherwood number with various physical parameters for $\omega = \pi/2$ and $\omega = \pi/6$, respectively and it is notable that reduced Nusselt number increases with Pr , Bi_1 , β , Sc and decreases with Pr , Nb , Nt , α , Bi_2 for both values of inclination angle ω . The local Sherwood number rises with growing values of Nt , β , Bi_1 and reduces with growing values of Nb , Bi_2 , α and Sc for both inclined and non-inclined MHD.

Conclusion

In current study we have investigated the impacts of an aligned magnetic and electric field ,thermal radiation on time dependent flow of Williamson nanofluid across a vertically stretched sheet. The set of formulated ordinary differential equations solve by bvp4c solver. Some important results of current study discussed as:

1. The large values of Unsteadiness parameter(s), Magnetic parameter(M), Weissenberg parameter(We), K lessening the fluid velocity.
2. The growing values of λ_1 , λ_2 and Local electric number Eenhances the fluid velocity.
3. With an increment of Biot number Bi1, Nt, Nb, R and Q, the fluid temperature increases.
4. With an elevation of Pr and thermal slip number α , the fluid temperature reduces.
5. The rising of Bi2 and Thermophoresis parameter Nt increases concentration profiles.
6. An enhancement in Brownian motion parameter Nb, Kr and Schmidt number Sc reduces concentration of nano particles.

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